

PILGRIMAGE TOURISM DESCRIBED AS A TYPE OF RELIGIOUS TOURISM

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Annotation: *This article describes the definition of religious tourism and the relationship between religious tourism and pilgrimage tourism.*

Keywords: *pilgrimage tourism, religious tourism, domestic tourism*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada diniy turizmning ta'rifi, diniy turizm va ziyorat turizmining bog'liqligi yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ziyosat turizmi, diniy turizm, ichki turizm, tashqi turizm*

Аннотация: *В данной статье описывается определение религиозного туризма и взаимосвязь между религиозным туризмом и паломническим туризмом.*

Ключевые слова: *паломнический туризм, религиозный туризм, внутренний туризм.*

The religious type of tourism has a rich history and at the same time plays an important role in the modern system of international and domestic tourism. As thousands of years ago, people travel to holy places, religious centers, strive to participate in sacred rites and ceremonies, pray, make sacrifices. Despite the rapid development of science and technology, religion continues to maintain a strong position in modern culture. Religious tourism is generally considered a separate type of tourism, in which the motivation for travel is based on the desire to visit the monuments of religious culture. Religious tourism includes activities related to the provision of travel services and meeting the needs of tourists to the holy places and religious centers outside the usual environment. According to the concepts of tourism, a tourist traveling for religious purposes is a person who travels outside the usual environment for less than a year to visit holy places and religious centers. has been constantly improved, so that the population's opportunities to visit the spiritual centers of different religions have significantly expanded. In addition, not only pilgrims of the relevant religion, but also tourists who want to join the spiritual achievements of different countries and peoples, to understand the essence of their beliefs travel to the holy places. There are two main types of religious tourism : pilgrimage

tourism and religious excursion tourism. The organization of tourist trips within them has important features.

Historically, the first type of religious tourism was pilgrimage. The word “pilgrimage” comes from the word “palm tree” - in the Middle Ages, Christian pilgrims who traveled to the Holy Land brought a palm branch from there. In science, pilgrimage is understood as a socio-cultural historical event, the essence of which is the travel of monks and secular figures to worship religious shrines, visit holy places and participate in religious celebrations.

Pilgrimage tourism is a type of religious tourism that involves travel of people of different faiths for pilgrimage purposes: worship at a shrine, temple, or other religious site; to hold or participate in a religious ceremony; spiritual improvement, grace, mental or physical healing; counsel (from the elders, from the people of God); the fulfillment of a vow, the atonement of sin ... It encourages people to visit for a variety of reasons. The most common aspirations include: getting rid of physical or mental illness; praying for family and friends; find divine grace; doing good work (construction, cleaning the monastery area, etc.); to give thanks to the higher powers for the blessings they have sent; devotion to the true faith, testing one's intentions and readiness for asceticism, finding the meaning of life. Pilgrimage, which is a type of religious tourism, is very diverse. For example, individually, family and group visitors are distinguished by the number of participants and family affiliation. The trip is divided into long and short visits according to the duration. In Russian Orthodox tradition, a journey lasting more than 10 days is generally accepted as a pilgrimage. Depending on the location of the religious monuments, the visit can be local or foreign.

Experts distinguish between spiritual and pilgrimage tourism, which has its own socio-psychological characteristics and a certain geographical direction, as a specific subtype of pilgrimage. We usually talk about the trips of tourists from Western countries to various spiritual practices in Eastern countries, primarily India, as well as China, Tibet, Nepal, Japan. In India, such tourists are attracted by ashrams - special centers of meditation, yoga, philosophy led by spiritual teachers, many of which are world famous. Ashrams are universal in nature and are open to people of different religions, nationalities, genders, ages, professions. Such mental practices are designed to help a person solve their problems, improve their spiritual and moral self, and know their “I”. The same can be said of the Chan Buddhist monasteries in China, where Shaolin preserves spiritual and martial arts traditions. Their participants consider religious objects as cultural

monuments, symbols of history, the most important part of the overall cultural and historical heritage. Participation in such trips is not strictly related to the religious affiliation of the travelers.

Tourists get acquainted with existing and memorable shrines, museums and exhibitions, participate in prayer ceremonies, voluntarily participate in religious events (processions, meditations, etc.). Excursions and religious tourism of the enlightenment direction are associated with a number of restrictions for tourists. Visiting places of worship requires strict adherence to rules such as the requirements for tourists' clothing and appearance. Representatives of other religions are not always allowed to participate in religious activities. For example, some Hindu temples are only open to Hindus. Mecca is a holy city for Muslims, where members of other religions are not allowed to enter.

However, unlike sightseeing and educational tours, travelers make extensive use of the existing tourist infrastructure (hotel accommodation, meals in ordinary cafes and restaurants, etc.). Excursions and educational trips are shorter, they do not coincide with religious holidays, in which both adults and children can participate. Tourists also visit religious monuments during combined trips. For example, an excursion to the sights of the historical center of St. Petersburg includes a tour of the Cathedrals of Kazan, St. Isaac, the Resurrection, a trip to Vladimir - a visit to the Association and Dmitrovsky Cathedrals. In both cases, getting acquainted with the temples is only part of the overall program. If the guide information is valuable in itself for ordinary tourists visiting religious sites, the excursion for pilgrims has a secondary, subordinate meaning to religious activity. It is obvious that pilgrims and tourists need highly qualified travel organizers and guides who have a thorough understanding of the divine and artistic features of religious sites and understand the specifics of religious psychology.

Experts also distinguish types of tourist activities, such as scientific tourism on a religious theme. This field includes research trips of religious scholars, historians, culturologists, ethnographers, archeologists and other scientists. Scholars are fascinated by the religious heritage of the past - ancient objects of worship, ancient sacred texts, traditions and legends. Special expeditions are often organized to study them. Researchers visit not only the recognized centers of existing religions (Vatican, Jerusalem, Mecca), but also areas where extinct religions (ancient Egypt, ancient Greece, ancient Rome, etc.) are recognized.

In general, religious tourism and its individual types are available in various organizational forms. Religious trips may or may not be organized.

The first of these is strictly regulated and is usually done on a prepaid basis. The seller and the customer discuss in advance the direction, duration of stay, the package of services provided (full package or only a number of services).

On unorganized travel, travelers do not turn to intermediary firms offering their tourism products, they plan and carry out the trip themselves. The advantage of unorganized travel is that the tourist is not tied to a strictly defined set of activities, but can flexibly build his or her route according to different circumstances.

Internal conditions include psychological motives that influence the decision to visit certain places, external factors - the financial situation of the tourist, which depends on the ability to pay for certain services; learn about new interesting items during the trip. This may include changes in weather conditions, as well as the emergence or escalation of various religious and (or) political conflicts. There are individual and group types depending on the number of participants in the trip. The number of participants in the individual round is 1-5 people, and in the group round - 6 or more people. Some travel companies consider group travel for 2 or more people. A special case of an individual species may be a person's journey. Often this can be observed on pilgrimage trips, which can take several months, unlike trips to attractions. One is very eager to retire to communicate with prayer, to think about inner problems, difficult life situations. And he goes alone to visit a monastery or other place.

Depending on the duration, the trips are divided into one-day, multi-day and multi-day trips. Experts divide day trips into trips that last less than 3 hours; 3-5 hours; 6-8 hours; 9-11 p.m. ; More than 12 hours (one day). Depending on the age of the travelers, children traveling with their parents can be young people (15-24 years old), much younger, economically active people (25-44 years old), economically active middle-aged people (45-64 years old). old), usually traveling without children, retirees (over 65 years).

Tourists use a variety of vehicles while traveling. They can reach their destinations by air, rail, road, sea, river transport. Different modes of transport can be used at different stages of the journey. For example, if the visit or excursion is made away from the traveler's place of residence, he or she may use air or rail transportation. And when traveling on local routes and (or) short distances - in the car. At certain stages of the pilgrimage or at certain parts of the route, pilgrims may not use any means of transportation on foot. It is asceticism due to a conscious intention to take on challenges in

order to strengthen oneself on the spiritual path. However, there may or may not be opportunities to use certain vehicles.

Religious tourism can vary depending on the regional and country characteristics of the trip. If pilgrims or tourists travel in their own country, it is domestic tourism. Inbound tourism is the visit of citizens of another country to the country. Outbound tourism is the travel of citizens of the respective state on a tourist trip to other countries.

The development of religious tourism in the modern world depends on the availability of appropriate resources. The need for this type of tourism is evident in the presence of religious objects - monasteries, shrines, temples and temple complexes, churches, churches, stupa; natural objects - sacred springs, wells, mountains, reservoirs (rivers, pools), groves; small places of worship are crosses on the side of the road, altars of gods on the sides of roads, paths, and so on. These objects may be located together. For example, the holy spring may be located in an Orthodox monastery or separately. Many Shinto shrines include places of worship and natural sites (shrines in a sacred garden by the water). According to experts, the sanctuary is a place of great importance for members of a particular religious denomination, where religious and other events are held, which gather many pilgrims. In such places there is a temple where a miraculous icon or a famous saint, a spiritual teacher, a former ascetic or a historical religious event takes place. A religious center is a broader concept than a "holy place." This includes, in addition to shrines, the administrative bodies of educational institutions and (or) religious organizations.

Religious tourists can use both collective and individual accommodation facilities. Collective accommodation buildings are usually divided into three groups: hotels and their analogues (motels, accommodation clubs, furnished rooms, etc.); specialized accommodation facilities (camps, land and water transport, etc.); other residential buildings (complexes of houses and bungalows, tents for pilgrims, monasteries, ashrams and other dormitories, etc.). Individual housing facilities are apartments, rooms in apartments, houses, cottages for rent and more.

Tourists traveling to the holy places, religious centers use the services of public catering establishments. It can be:

1. Restaurants, cafes, eateries, etc. In religious centers, a number of sacred sites, pilgrims and tourists can use the services of these institutions and have a choice of food.

2. Monastery, Ashram and other kitchens, etc., where food is prepared for guests. The range of dishes here is different from the dishes offered in

cafes and restaurants. In some cases the food may be simpler, lean during Orthodox Lent, vegetarian in Indian ashram (spicy or non-spicy). Visitors are often served food at set times, often without food selection. The idea that voluntary self-restraint is only beneficial and leads to spiritual growth is also expressed here.

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